

INFLUENCE OF DEFECT SHAPE AND POSITION ON THE HIGH CYCLE FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF ADDITIVELY MANUFACTURED TA6V ALLOY

M. Bonneric¹, N. Saintier¹, D. El-Khoukhi² & J. Bega¹

The presence of process induced defects in parts produced by Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) is today a well-known issue. It is therefore crucial to account for the defects when designing additively manufactured components against fatigue. To address this question TA6V samples with different defect populations have been produced by varying the process parameters. These defect populations have been characterised using X-ray tomography, while the samples have been subjected to uniaxial fatigue testing ($R=-1$). The results have demonstrated the detrimental impact of lack-of-fusion defects as compared to the gas pores for the case of surface crack initiation. In addition, the control of the distance between the defective areas and the surface of the samples allowed for the investigation of the criticality of internal defects. The establishment of a Kitagawa diagram for internal defects highlighted that the criticality of internal defects does not depend on the defect type, as opposed to surface defects.

Keywords: High Cycle Fatigue, Laser Powder Bed Fusion, Defect, TA6V

INTRODUCTION

Processing parts by laser powder bed fusion (L-PBF) technology usually involves the generation of defects such as gas pores or lack-of-fusion (LoF) defects (DebRoy [1], Zhang [2]). These defects are known to be the main cause for the fatigue damage of additively manufactured (AM) parts, along with the surface roughness, and their detrimental impact on the fatigue strength has been clearly evidenced, in particular for the Ti-6Al-4V alloy (see Le et al [3] for example). Accounting for the presence of defects in the fatigue design methodologies is therefore a crucial issue to guarantee the reliability of AM components.

The existing literature on the fatigue behaviour of defective materials indicates that the main defect features that impact on the fatigue strength are the size, position with respect to the surface, shape, and nature (Murakami [4]). This is also true for the typical defects induced by L-PBF. For the case of Ti-6Al-4V alloy most of the works show that the fatigue cracks usually initiate at surface or subsurface defects (see Wycisk [5] and Günther [6]), as it is common in the High Cycle Fatigue (HCF) regime. In addition Pessard et al [7] established a Kitagawa-Takahashi diagram for the LoF defects, which describes the evolution of the fatigue resistance as a function of the critical defect size, thus demonstrating the sensitivity of the fatigue behaviour to the defect size. LoF defects are often designated as the most harmful defects due to intense stress concentrations.

1. Arts et Métiers Institute of Technology, University of Bordeaux, CNRS, Bordeaux INP, INRAE, HESAM Université, I2M Bordeaux, F-33400 Talence, France
2. Centre Technique des Industries Mécaniques (CETIM), Senlis, France,

However in most cases they are larger than gas pores, and the studies aiming to discriminate the impacts of the size and shape, the latter one being significantly different between gas pores and LoF defects, are very limited for AM materials. In the work of Le et al [8], the differences in shapes (gas pores or LoF) was found responsible for a high scatter of fatigue test results for Ti-6Al-4V alloy, along with the defect position. This conclusion is consistent with a paper from Nadot [9] where the fatigue behaviour of conventional Ti-6AL-4V alloy was more sensitive to the local defect morphology as compared with other alloys.

The aim of the present work is to discriminate the impact of the main defect features (size, position, shape) on the fatigue behaviour of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy processed by L-PBF. To do so samples with different defect populations have been produced varying the process parameters. The defect populations have been characterised by means of X-ray tomography, and a fatigue test campaign has been conducted to determine the defect criticality in the HCF regime. The results have been discussed after observing the fracture surfaces and determining the Kitagawa-Takahashi diagrams for all defect populations.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample production

All samples were produced on a SLM 280HL powder machine on the additive manufacturing platform of I2M institute (FUTURPROD), using Ti-6Al-4V powder (20-63µm). Three different sets of process parameters were used in order to obtain different defect populations. These sets are provided in Table 1 as well as the corresponding volume energy density E_v defined as:

$$E_v = \frac{P}{v \times h \times t} \tag{1}$$

where P , v , h , and t are the laser power, scan velocity, hatch spacing, and layer thickness, respectively. The first set is designated as Ref and corresponds to the parameters recommended by the manufacturer to process the material with the highest density. The second one is designated as PG and corresponds to a high energy density promoting the development of gas pores, while the third one, designated as LOF, corresponds to a low energy density leading to the formation of LoF defects. Note that the same stripe scanning strategy with an angle of 15° between subsequent layers was used for all samples, and that the build plate was heated to 200°C.

TABLE 1 Sets of process parameters used to produce the samples

Parameter set	P (W)	v (mm/s)	t (mm)	h (mm)	E_v (J/mm ³)
Ref	275	1100	0.03	0.12	69
PG	275	400	0.03	0.12	191
LOF	100	200	0.09	0.09	62

Several batches of vertical fatigue specimens were produced. Figure 1 illustrates the main details in terms of defects for the different batches, whose descriptions are provided below:

- Batch Ref corresponds to samples fully processed using the Ref set of parameters.
- Batch PG – S corresponds to samples fully processed using the PG set of parameters.
- Batch LOF – S for which samples have been fully processed using the LOF set of parameters.
- Batch PG – I corresponds to samples processed combining the Ref and PG sets of parameters. The Ref strategy was applied to the subsurface volume while the PG strategy was applied to the core, as illustrated in Figure 1. By doing so, gas pores were only introduced in the bulk of the samples with the aim of assessing the criticality of internal defects. The depth of the subsurface volume scanned with the Ref strategy was 1mm after the machining of the specimen surface.
- Batch LOF – I corresponds to samples processed combining the Ref and LOF sets of parameters in the same manner as for batch PG – I, resulting in LoF defects only in the core of the samples.

FIGURE 1: Defect populations introduced in the batches of fatigue specimens.

Note that after manufacturing all samples were subjected to a stress-relief treatment (2h / 704°C) as recommended by AMS 2801 standard, and their surfaces were finally machined in order to avoid any influence of the surface roughness on the fatigue behaviour.

Microstructure, micro-hardness measurements

Figure 2 shows the microstructures corresponding to the aforementioned sets of process parameters. In all cases a fine martensitic microstructure was obtained due to the high cooling rates involved with L-PBF, consistently with the literature (see Kasperovitch and Hausmann [10] for example). Note that the ex-beta grains elongated in the building direction (BD) can also be observed on these pictures.

FIGURE 2: Microstructures corresponding to the building strategies Ref (a), PG (b), and LOF (c).

Micro-hardness measurements were performed with a Vicker indenter and a loading of 1kg. 20 measures have been made with an in-between distance of 0.5mm for each sample. The results are provided in Table 2. They indicate that the differences in the process parameters used for the study result in minor changes in the hardness values (<10%). As a direct correlation between hardness

and fatigue strength is observed for many metallic alloys [4], these results suggest that the potential differences between the investigated microstructures will not significantly impact their fatigue behaviour, all the more since the defects are much larger than the typical length of the martensitic microstructure.

TABLE 2 Micro-hardness characterisations of the different building strategies

	Ref	PG	LOF
HV1	367 ± 6	390 ± 9	362 ± 9

Defect populations

The defect populations corresponding to the Ref, PG and LOF strategies have been characterised using X-ray tomography. To do so one cylindrical sample (Ø3 x 10mm) was scanned with a voxel size of 2µm for each strategy. Figures 3 provides views of the observed defects as well as the cumulative defect size distributions associated to the strategies LOF and PG. Note that this distribution was not calculated for the Ref strategy as only few defects were found in the corresponding sample (see Figure 3.a). By comparing Figure 3.b and 3.c it can be seen that the defect density, meaning the number of defect per volume unit, is much higher for the PG strategy than for the LOF one. However the largest LoF defects are twice to three times larger than the largest gas pores, as shown in Figure 3.d. It is also worth noting that the variability in the defect sizes is much greater for the LoF defects.

FIGURE 3: 3D views of the defects observed by X-ray tomography for the Ref strategy (a), LOF strategy (b), PG strategy (c) - and associated cumulative defect size distributions (d)

Fatigue testing procedure

All fatigue tests were performed under uniaxial tensile loads with a load ratio $R = -1$ using a Zwick resonant machine. They were performed in air, at room temperature, at a frequency of approximately 110Hz, and following a staircase procedure. The maximum number of cycles for a test was 2×10^6 cycles. The run-out samples were tested again at higher stress levels until failure was reached, in order to identify the most critical defect in the sample from SEM observations of the fracture surfaces. Steps of 20MPa in terms of stress amplitude were used for this procedure. The latter one made also possible to assess the fatigue strength for each specimen that did not fail after a first step, by following the formula proposed by Lanning et al [11]:

$$\sigma_D = \sigma_{n-1} + (\sigma_n - \sigma_{n-1}) \times \frac{N_f}{2 \times 10^6} \quad (2)$$

where σ_D is the interpolated fatigue strength at 2×10^6 cycles, σ_{n-1} the stress amplitude of the test prior to the one where failure occurs, σ_n is the stress level of the final test during which failure occurs, and N_f is the number of cycles to failure in the final test. Note that the use of this formula relies on the assumption that no damage occurs before the final test.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

S-N curves and fracture surface observations

Figure 4 shows the S-N curves obtained for the different batches of fatigue samples. Note that the final fatigue lives of the specimens tested at different stress levels were not reported on this graph. This is the reason why the specimens from the Ref strategy do not appear on this figure, as all of them had to be tested again to reach failure. The examination of all fracture surfaces indicated that for all specimens produced using the PG and LOF strategies, the critical fatigue cracks initiated at gas pores and LoF defects, respectively. As expected, the critical fatigue cracks initiated at surface defects for PG – S and LOF – S samples, and at internal defects for the PG – I and LOF – I samples. In addition, the fatigue cracks in the specimens processed using the Ref strategy all initiated at internal gas pores of sizes $\sqrt{A} \sim 50\mu\text{m}$, where $\sqrt{A}$ is the Murakami parameter [4]. Figure 5 provides illustrations of the typical defects observed in each batch of specimens.

In Figure 4, apart from the fact that the LoF defects are more critical than the gas pores as commonly observed in the literature, one can note the significant impact of the defect position on the fatigue resistance, internal defects being much less critical. This effect is more pronounced for the LoF defects, as already observed in [8], the fatigue strength for internal LoF defects being almost four times higher than for surface LoF defects.

FIGURE 4: S-N curves obtained after fatigue tests (R = -1)

Figure 6 shows the cumulative distribution of the critical defect sizes for the different batches, determined from the defect size measurements performed on the SEM pictures of the fracture surfaces. One can note that for internal defects the critical defect sizes are similar to sizes of the upper tails of the distributions shown in Figure 3.d, corresponding to the X-ray tomography characterisations. However for the surface defects, the critical defects are much smaller and the scatter in their sizes is reduced. This result can be interpreted as follows. The subsurface volume where the critical fatigue cracks are likely to initiate in LOF – S and PG – S samples is much smaller than the core volume where internal cracks initiate in LOF – I and PG – I samples. The probability of finding a defect of a given size is therefore less in the subsurface volume than in the core volume, resulting in smaller critical defects in LOF – S and PG – S samples than in LOF – I and PG – I samples.

FIGURE 5: SEM observations of the typical critical defects found in Ref (a), LOF - S (b), PG - S (c), LOF- I (d), and PG - I (e) batches

FIGURE 6: Cumulative size distributions of the critical defects observed in the different batches of fatigue specimens

Kitagawa-Takahashi diagrams

By testing again at higher stress levels the specimens that did not fail after a first fatigue test, it was possible to assess the particular fatigue strength at 2×10^6 cycles corresponding to each of these specimens. The Kitagawa diagrams of the different specimen batches were then determined by using measurements of the critical defect sizes obtained from SEM observations. The obtained diagrams are provided in Figure 7.

FIGURE 7: Kitagawa diagrams determined for the different specimen batches

In addition to the experimental data points, several models aiming to predict the evolution of the fatigue with respect to the defect size were represented with dashed lines in Figure 7. The first model, designated as LEFM, is based on fracture mechanics, and consists in considering the defect as an existing crack that will propagate if the stress intensity factor amplitude is greater than a threshold value ΔK_{th} . In this case the fatigue strength σ_D can be expressed as a function of the defect size $\sqrt{A}$ using the following formula:

$$\sigma_D = \frac{\Delta K_{th}}{Y\sqrt{\pi\sqrt{A}}} \tag{3}$$

where Y is a coefficient whose value is 0.65 for the case of surface defects [4]. This LEFM was represented in Figure 7 for two ΔK_{th} values, $2.6MPa\sqrt{m}$ which seems to fit the experimental data for the batch PG – S, and $1.6MPa\sqrt{m}$ which seems to fit the experimental data for the batch LOF – S. The second model represented in Figure 7 is the phenomenological law proposed by Murakami [4] to assess the fatigue strength at $R = -1$ knowing the hardness HV and defect size $\sqrt{A}$, corresponding to the following equation:

$$\sigma_D = \frac{C(HV + 120)}{\sqrt{A}^{1/6}} \tag{4}$$

where C is a coefficient of value 1.56 (only valid for internal defects). This model seems to provide an acceptable description of all experimental internal defects results.

DISCUSSION

The Kitagawa diagrams shown in Figure 7 demonstrate the sensitivity of the fatigue behaviour to the defect size. In particular, one can see that the criticality of the surface gas pores (PG- S) is well depicted with a LEFM model. This is also the case for the surface LoF defects, although the scatter in the fatigue strengths is higher than for the gas pores. One can assume that this increased scatter results from more variability in terms of local geometries for the LoF defects, as compared to the gas pores. In addition, it is worth noting that the criticality of all surface defects cannot be depicted with one single LEFM model, as it appears that accounting for the LoF defects involves a ΔK_{th} value 40% less than the one used for gas pores. This result is yet consistent with the intense stress concentrations induced by a LoF defect, which is expected to be more critical than a gas pore of the same size and loaded with the same macroscopic stress.

When considering the Kitagawa diagrams for internal defects, one can see that all defect types are positioned on a same trend and that the effect of the size on the fatigue strength is less pronounced than for the surface defects. The latter result could be due to the increase in the crack propagation stage when internal defects are involved. Indeed, it is usually assumed that the fatigue cracks initiated at internal defect propagate as under vacuum, meaning without any assistance of the ambient air that increases the fatigue crack growth rate in many metals (see Junet et al [12] work on conventional Ti-6Al-4V for example). This means that for a given applied stress, a crack initiated at an internal defect propagates much slower than a crack initiated at a surface defect. As a result, decreasing the applied stress could increase the crack propagation stage in a more significant way for internal defects than for surface defects, meaning that the contribution of the propagation stage to the fatigue strength would be greater for internal defects. For the case of internal defects, the fatigue strength would be therefore less sensitive to the defect features, and in particular to the defect size which is known to be a critical parameter for crack initiation.

CONCLUSION

In this work, the fatigue behaviour of the Ti-6Al-4V processed by AM was studied for different defect populations, namely LoF defects and gas pores. The Kitagawa diagram of the alloy was determined for these two types of defect, discriminating for each type the internal and surface defects. For the case of surface defects, LEFM model is able to predict the fatigue strength, but the ΔK_{th} value to be used for LoF defects is reduced by 40% compared to the gas pores. The results also showed that the effect of the defect size is less pronounced for internal defects, with no significant difference between LoF and gas pores. The latter result was attributed to a significant increase in the crack propagation stage for internal defects, making the fatigue strength less sensitive to the defect responsible for the crack initiation and its features. However this assumption would deserve a closer examination by characterising the fatigue crack propagation of the Ti-6Al-4V processed by L-PBF under air and vacuum.

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) DebRoy, T., Wei, H.L., Zuback, J.S., Mukherjee, T., Elmer, J.W., Milewski, J.O., Beese, A.M., Wilson-Heid, A., De, A., and Zhang, W., *Prog.Mater. Sci.*, Vol. 92, 2018, pp. 112–224.

- (2) Zhang, B., Li, Y., and Bai, Q., *Chin. J. Mech. Eng.*, Vol. 30, 2017, pp. 515-527.
- (3) Le, V.D., Pessard, E., Morel, F., and Edy, F., *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, Vol. 214, 2019, pp. 410-426.
- (4) Murakami, Y., *Metal Fatigue: Effect of Small Defects and Nonmetallic Inclusions*, Elsevier, 2002.
- (5) Wycisk, E., Emmelmann, C., Siddique, S., and Walther, F., *Adv. Mater. Res.*, Vols. 816-817, 2013, pp. 134-139
- (6) Günther, J., Krewerth, D., Lippmann, T., Leuders, S., Tröster, T., Weidner, A., Biermann, H., and Niendorf, T., *Int. J. Fat.*, Vol. 94, 2017, pp. 236-245
- (7) Pessard, E., Lavialle, M., Laheurte, P., Didier, P., and Brochu, M., *Int. J. Fat.*, Vol. 149, 2021
- (8) Le, V.D., Pessard, E., Morel, F., and Prigent, S., *Int. J. Fat.*, Vol. 140, 2020
- (9) Nadot, Y., *Int. J. Fat.*, Vol. 154, 2022
- (10) Kasperovitch, G., and Hausmann, J., *J. Mater. Process. Technol.*, Vol. 220, 2015, pp. 202-214
- (11) Lanning, D.B., Nicholas, T., and Haritos, G.K., *Int. J. Fat.*, Vol. 27, No. 1, 2005, pp. 45-57
- (12) Junet, A., Messenger, A., Weck, A., Nadot, Y., Boulnat, X., and Buffière, J-Y., *Int. J. Fat.*, Vol. 168, 2023